

AXIAL COMPRESSION TESTS ON SQUARE FRP-CONFINED T-SECTION-STIFFENED DOUBLE-SKIN TUBULAR COLUMNS

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP)-concrete-steel double-skin tubular columns (DSTCs) have emerged as a promising type of columns with excellent durability and ductility. This paper presents a series of axial compression tests on a variation of hybrid DSTCs, namely, square FRP-confined T-section-stiffened DSTCs (i.e., T-DSTCs). The new characteristic of T-DSTCs is the utilization of T-section stiffeners for the steel tube; the additional stiffeners not only provide restraints against the potential local buckling of steel tube, but also provide extra confinement to the concrete close to the flat sides of FRP tube which is otherwise ineffectively confined. The experimental results demonstrate the excellent structural performance of T-DSTCs.

KEYWORDS

FRP-confined concrete; Double-skin tubular columns; Hybrid columns; T-section stiffeners; Compressive behaviour

INTRODUCTION

Hybrid fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP)-concrete-steel double-skin tubular columns (DSTCs) consist of an external FRP tube, an internal steel tube, and an annular concrete infill between the two tubes (Teng et al., 2007). As an emerging form of high-performance structural members, hybrid DSTCs have many advantages over conventional reinforced concrete (RC) columns and concrete-filled tubular columns. Confined by the FRP tube, the strength and deformability of concrete in DSTCs are significantly enhanced. In addition, the FRP tube forms a natural anti-corrosion sleeve which can effectively protect the steel tube, while the steel tube acts as reinforcement for improved flexural stiffness and strength. As a result of the optimized combination of the three materials, hybrid DSTCs possess high strength and stiffness, excellent ductility as well as durability (Yu, 2007).

Compared with circular columns, square columns are often preferred in buildings due to their ease for construction and/or for aesthetic reasons (Yu and Teng, 2013; Li et al., 2020). For DSTCs with a square FRP tube, however, their performance may be significantly inferior to their counterparts with a circular FRP tube, as the flat sides of the square tube offers rather weak confinement to the concrete (Yu and Teng, 2013). Furthermore, the inner steel tube may suffer from inward buckling although their outward buckling is constrained by the concrete (Yu and Teng, 2013; Guo et al., 2020). To address these issues, a novel variation of DSTCs was recently proposed by the last author. The novel column form, referred to as square FRP-confined T-section-stiffened DSTCs (i.e., T-DSTCs), involves the use of four symmetrical T-section stiffeners for the inner steel tube (Figure 1a). The T-section stiffeners provides effective constraints for the potential inward buckling of the steel tube, while their flanges provide extra confinement to the concrete close to flat sides of FRP tube. The thickness of the inner steel tube can be significantly reduced while the stiffeners can also be thin without ductility issues because they are both encased by the concrete; the structural function of FRP outer tube is mainly to confine the concrete but not to provide longitudinal stiffness and strength, so it also does not have to be thick. Therefore, T-DSTCs are expected to be cost-effective. Furthermore, the T-section stiffeners facilitate the placement of the FRP tube during construction and allow easy connection to other structural components. This paper presents a series of compression tests which were designed to demonstrate the structural concept of square T-DSTCs.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Test Specimens

Four specimens, including a pair of T-DSTCs and a pair of normal DSTCs (i.e., without stiffeners, see Figure 1b), were tested; each pair consisted of two identical specimens. Each specimen possessed a square filament-wound FRP tube with four rounded corners. Three plies of glass fibers, with a nominal thickness of 0.17 mm per ply, were wound in the angle of $\pm 89.7^\circ$ to the longitudinal axis of the tube. Dimensions of the steel tube and the T-stiffener are summarized in Table 1, where the specimens having a name starting with “T-” are T-DSTCs while those having a name starting with “D-” are normal DSTCs.

Figure 1 Cross-sections of (a) T-DSTC, (b) DSTC

Table 1 Details of the specimens

Specimen	H (mm)	b (mm)	r (mm)	d (mm)	t (mm)	t_w (mm)	t_f (mm)	h_w (mm)	b_f (mm)
D-3F-I	500	200	25	114	4.0	-	-	-	-
D-3F-II	500	200	25	114	4.0	-	-	-	-
T-3F-I	500	200	25	114	4.0	5.5	5.5	43	80
T-3F-II	500	200	25	114	4.0	5.5	5.5	43	80

Note: H – the height of the specimen; b – the inner side length of the FRP tube; r – the radius of the rounded corners in the FRP tube; d – the diameter of the circular tube; t – the thickness of the circular tube; t_w – the thickness of the stiffener’s web, t_f – the thickness of the stiffener’s flange, h_w – the height of the stiffener’s web; b_f – the width of the stiffener’s flange.

Material properties

The FRP tube had a tensile strength of 2580 MPa and an elastic modulus of 80.1 GPa in the fibre direction, based on a nominal thickness of 0.17 mm per ply, according to the data from the supplier. The average compressive strength of concrete was 108.39 MPa based on the results of standard concrete cylinders tests. For each type of inner tubes (i.e., with and without stiffeners), two hollow steel tubes which were nominally identical to those used in the DSTCs/T-DSTCs were tested under axial compression to obtain their full-range load-axial strain curves.

Test set-up and instrumentation

As shown in Figure 2, four LVDTs (L1 to L4) were installed on the four sides of each specimen to measure the axial deformation of the 200 mm mid-height region, while another of four LVDTs (L5 to L8) were used to measure the overall shortening of the specimen. Eight transverse strain gauges (SG1 to SG8, see Figure 3) were installed on the FRP tube. For DSTCs, two axial strain gauges (SG9 and SG10, see Figure 3) were installed on the steel tube; For T-DSTCs, besides SG9 and SG10, four transverse strain gauges (SG11, SG13, SG15 and SG17) and four axial strain gauges (SG12, SG14, SG16 and SG18) were installed on the webs of the stiffeners; meanwhile, four axial strain gauges (SG19

~ SG22) were installed on stiffeners' flanges (Figure 3). All the specimens were tested with a displacement control rate of 0.3 mm/min.

Figure 2 Test setup and the layout of LVDTs.

Figure 3 Layout of strain gauges.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

General behaviour

(a) (b)
Figure 4 Failure modes: (a) D-3F-II; (b) T-3F-I.

All specimens showed a similar failure mode (see Figure 4), which is characterized by the rupture of the FRP tube at the corners and the crushing of the concrete at the same position. Inward buckling of the steel tube was not observed in all the specimens due to the relatively small diameter-to-thickness ratio (i.e., 28.5) of the steel tube.

Axial load-axial strain behaviour

The DSTC specimens showed quite different axial load-strain behaviour compared to the T-DSTC specimens, as shown in Figure 5. The former experienced a sudden, significant load drop (by up to 39% of the peak load) at the peak load, accompanied with several horizontal cracks of the FRP tube induced by the compressive failure of the resin matrix; the specimens were able to recover only a small amount of their load capacity afterwards because of the FRP confinement. By contrast, T-DSTCs only experienced a slight load drop (by around 3.5% of the peak load) at the peak load, and were able to sustain approximately the same load with a large ultimate axial strain until rupture of FRP.

Table 2 compares peak loads of specimens measured in the tests (N_e) and the nominal strength of the section (N_n). N_n is obtained by superposing N_c and N_s , where N_c equals to the concrete cross-sectional area times the unconfined concrete strength; N_s is the load taken by the inner tube, which was obtained by the load-axial strain relation measured from the hollow steel tube test and the axial strain level of the inner tube when the peak load of specimen was reached. As listed in Table 2, N_e/N_n of the DSTC specimens is slightly less than 1.0, suggesting that the confinement effect on the concrete strength was minor for these specimens; this was due to the relatively thin FRP tube used in the tests and their square shape. By contrast, it can be seen that the peak loads of the two T-DSTC specimens, which had the same FRP tube as the DSTC specimens, are 13% and 22% higher than their nominal strengths, respectively, indicating a considerable enhancement on the concrete compressive strength.

Table 2 Comparison of experimental peak load and nominal peak load

Specimen	N_c (kN)	N_s (kN)	N_e (kN)	N_n (kN)	N_e / N_n (kN)
D-3F-I	3171.058	119.31	2987.09	3290.37	0.91
D-3F-II	3171.058	197.68	2940.33	3368.74	0.87
T-3F-I	2877.755	682.02	4038.46	3559.77	1.13
T-3F-II	2877.755	683.41	4337.07*	3561.16	1.22

*The loading of specimen T-3F-II was terminated at 4337.07 kN due to the capacity limit of the MTS machine.

Figure 5 Axial load-axial strain curves.

Transverse strain-axial strain curve

Figure 6 compares the transverse strain-axial strain curves of the DSTC and T-DSTC specimens. The transverse strains were averaged from the strain gauges at the corners and those at the flat sides, respectively; compressive strains are defined to be positive. It is evident from Figure 6 at a given axial strain, the transverse strain of the T-DSTC specimen is significantly smaller than that of the DSTC

specimen when the axial strain exceeded 0.003. This is largely attributed to the confinement from T-section stiffeners to the concrete, which further constrains the concrete expansion.

Figure 6 Transverse strain-axial strain curve.

CONCLUSIONS

A series of axial compression tests on square FRP-confined double-skin tubular columns (DSTCs) and square FRP-confined T-section-stiffened double-skin tubular columns (T-DSTCs) have been presented in this paper. It is evident from the test results that T-DSTCs possess significantly improved strength and ductility compared with normal DSTCs without T-stiffeners. T-section stiffeners provide effective extra confinement to the concrete at the flat side of the column and contribute to constraining the lateral expansion of the concrete.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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